

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Axial conduit widening, tree height and height growth rate set the hydraulic transition of sapwood into heartwood

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Content:

- Table S1
- Table S2
- Table S3
- Figure S1
- Figure S2
- Figure S3
- Figure S4

Table S1. Results of the optimal Bayesian models predicting the $\log_{10}DCA$ and $\log_{10}H$ effects on the hydraulic diameter in *P. abies* (A) and *F. sylvatica* (B) respectively. Disc number (N_{disc}) was used as random factor.

Model: $\log_{10}Dh \sim \log_{10}DCA + \log_{10}H + (N_{disc})$							
(A) <i>P. abies</i>							
	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept	0.96	0.02	0.93	0.99	1.00	1241	1399
$\log_{10}(DCA)$	0.14	0.00	0.14	0.15	1.00	5426	2509
$\log_{10}(H)$	0.06	0.01	0.04	0.09	1.00	1071	1420
Marginal $R^2 = 0.88$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.90$							
(B) <i>F. sylvatica</i>							
	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept	1.27	0.03	1.21	1.32	1.00	1416	2075
$\log_{10}(DCA)$	0.23	0.00	0.22	0.23	1.00	4854	3219
$\log_{10}(H)$	-0.18	0.02	-0.22	-0.14	1.00	1288	1512
Marginal $R^2 = 0.88$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.93$							

Table S2. Results of the optimal Bayesian models predicting the effects of $\log_{10}DCA$ and H classes on the hydraulic diameter in *P. abies* (A) and *F. sylvatica* (B) respectively. Disc number (N_{disc}) was used as random factor.

Model: $\log_{10}Dh \sim \log_{10}DCA + H_{CLASS} + (N_{disc})$							
(A) <i>P. abies</i>							
	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept ($H = 1$ m)	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.94	1.01	433	754
$\log_{10}(DCA)$	0.14	0.00	0.14	0.15	1.00	3386	2896
$H = 2$ m	0.95	0.01	0.92	0.97	1.00	659	1261
$H = 3$ m	0.99	0.01	0.97	1.02	1.01	589	1143
$H = 4$ m	1.01	0.01	0.99	1.04	1.00	565	1021
$H = 5$ m	1.04	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.00	569	1040
$H = 6$ m	1.04	0.01	1.01	1.07	1.00	622	1213
$H = 7$ m	1.05	0.01	1.02	1.08	1.00	544	949
$H = 8$ m	1.05	0.01	1.02	1.08	1.00	564	1092
$H = 9$ m	1.05	0.01	1.02	1.08	1.01	537	952
$H = 10$ m	1.04	0.01	1.01	1.07	1.01	566	1011
$H = 11$ m	1.04	0.01	1.02	1.07	1.01	481	842
$H = 12$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.00	493	855
$H = 13$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	466	878
$H = 14$ m	1.04	0.01	1.02	1.07	1.01	457	811
$H = 15$ m	1.04	0.01	1.02	1.06	1.01	440	811
$H = 16$ m	1.04	0.01	1.02	1.07	1.01	452	795
$H = 17$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	445	732
$H = 18$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	445	745
$H = 19$ m	1.04	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	438	778
$H = 20$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	432	761
$H = 21$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	434	744
$H = 22$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	433	759
$H = 23$ m	1.04	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	437	735
$H = 24$ m	1.04	0.01	1.02	1.07	1.01	428	698
$H = 25$ m	1.05	0.01	1.02	1.07	1.01	435	696
$H = 26$ m	1.03	0.01	1.01	1.06	1.01	428	760
Marginal $R^2 = 0.89$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.90$							

Model: $\log_{10}Dh \sim \log_{10}DCA + H_{CLASS} + (N_{disc})$

(B) *F. sylvatica*

	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept ($H = 2$ m)	1.02	0.09	0.85	1.19	1.01	497	940
$\log_{10}(H)$	0.36	0.06	0.24	0.48	1.01	494	962
$H = 3$ m	1.63	0.18	1.28	1.98	1.00	1841	4611
$H = 4$ m	1.28	0.38	0.53	2.04	1.00	6992	8675
$H = 5$ m	0.59	0.53	-0.46	1.63	1.00	9683	11259
$H = 6$ m	2.73	0.86	1.03	4.43	1.00	13358	12192
$H = 7$ m	1.24	0.09	1.05	1.42	1.01	590	1378
$H = 8$ m	1.00	0.09	0.82	1.18	1.01	578	1245
$H = 9$ m	1.27	0.10	1.07	1.46	1.01	622	1307
$H = 10$ m	0.97	0.11	0.75	1.19	1.01	837	2129
$H = 11$ m	1.15	0.13	0.90	1.41	1.01	1032	2785
$H = 12$ m	1.15	0.11	0.94	1.36	1.01	742	1976
$H = 13$ m	1.16	0.11	0.96	1.37	1.01	732	1785
$H = 14$ m	1.06	0.12	0.82	1.30	1.01	967	2862
$H = 15$ m	1.07	0.14	0.79	1.35	1.00	1285	3321
$H = 16$ m	1.20	0.10	1.00	1.41	1.01	729	1738
$H = 17$ m	1.20	0.10	1.00	1.40	1.01	683	1545
$H = 18$ m	1.25	0.11	1.04	1.46	1.01	734	1803
$H = 19$ m	1.29	0.13	1.05	1.54	1.01	1039	2832
$H = 20$ m	1.26	0.16	0.95	1.57	1.00	1578	4236
$H = 21$ m	0.90	0.10	0.70	1.09	1.01	697	1637
$H = 22$ m	0.93	0.11	0.70	1.15	1.01	888	2361
$H = 23$ m	1.00	0.10	0.80	1.20	1.01	685	1572
$H = 24$ m	0.99	0.13	0.73	1.26	1.01	1102	2904
$H = 25$ m	1.11	0.11	0.88	1.33	1.01	858	2247
$H = 26$ m	1.02	0.11	0.80	1.23	1.01	772	1865
$H = 27$ m	0.83	0.09	0.64	1.02	1.01	594	1306
$H = 28$ m	0.94	0.09	0.77	1.12	1.01	534	1137
$H = 29$ m	1.05	0.09	0.87	1.21	1.01	519	1057
$H = 30$ m	0.98	0.09	0.81	1.15	1.01	516	1079
$H = 31$ m	0.99	0.09	0.82	1.16	1.01	506	975
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 3$ m	-0.04	0.10	-0.24	0.16	1.00	1215	2880
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 4$ m	0.16	0.17	-0.19	0.50	1.00	3705	7083
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 5$ m	0.42	0.22	-0.01	0.86	1.00	5351	10141
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 6$ m	-0.41	0.34	-1.07	0.24	1.00	8970	11312
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 7$ m	0.17	0.06	0.05	0.29	1.01	521	1081
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 8$ m	0.26	0.06	0.14	0.39	1.01	523	1117
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 9$ m	0.17	0.06	0.04	0.29	1.01	533	1046
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 10$ m	0.27	0.07	0.14	0.40	1.01	595	1241
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 11$ m	0.21	0.07	0.08	0.35	1.01	643	1459
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 12$ m	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.34	1.01	558	1230
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 13$ m	0.21	0.06	0.08	0.33	1.01	558	1114
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 14$ m	0.24	0.07	0.11	0.37	1.01	619	1408
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 15$ m	0.23	0.07	0.09	0.38	1.01	693	1609
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 16$ m	0.19	0.06	0.07	0.32	1.01	552	1194
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 17$ m	0.19	0.06	0.07	0.32	1.01	541	1121
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 18$ m	0.16	0.06	0.04	0.29	1.01	548	1211

$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 19$ m	0.15	0.07	0.02	0.29	1.01	619	1380
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 20$ m	0.16	0.07	0.02	0.31	1.01	740	1942
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 21$ m	0.27	0.06	0.15	0.40	1.01	542	1156
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 22$ m	0.27	0.07	0.14	0.40	1.01	582	1308
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 23$ m	0.24	0.06	0.12	0.37	1.01	536	1058
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 24$ m	0.24	0.07	0.10	0.37	1.01	629	1380
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 25$ m	0.20	0.07	0.07	0.33	1.01	581	1278
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 26$ m	0.23	0.06	0.10	0.35	1.01	555	1199
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 27$ m	0.28	0.06	0.16	0.41	1.01	513	1051
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 28$ m	0.25	0.06	0.13	0.37	1.01	502	1003
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 29$ m	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.33	1.01	499	968
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 30$ m	0.23	0.06	0.12	0.35	1.01	498	997
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 31$ m	0.23	0.06	0.11	0.35	1.01	496	967
Marginal $R^2 = 0.94$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.94$							

Table S3. Results of the optimal linear mixed- effect models predicting the effects of $\log_{10}H$ (A) and ΔH classes (B) on the number of sapwood rings ($NSWr$), and (C) of $\log_{10}\Delta H$ and *Division* (conifers/angiosperms) on the mean width of sapwood rings ($SWrw$). *Species* was used as random factor.

(A) Model: $\log_{10}NSWr \sim \log_{10}H + \Delta H_{CLASS} + (Species)$							
	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept ($\Delta H=0\div 5$ cm)	1.19	0.09	1.01	1.36	1.01	610	952
$\log_{10}(H)$	0.34	0.04	0.26	0.43	1.00	668	1249
$\Delta H=5\div 10$ cm	0.98	0.05	0.89	1.08	1.00	889	1461
$\Delta H=10\div 15$ cm	0.69	0.05	0.59	0.78	1.00	889	1806
$\Delta H=15\div 20$ cm	0.70	0.06	0.58	0.82	1.00	1111	2069
$\Delta H=20\div 30$ cm	0.53	0.07	0.39	0.66	1.00	1333	2300
$\Delta H=30\div 40$ cm	0.26	0.06	0.14	0.39	1.00	1231	2398
$\Delta H=40\div 50$ cm	0.17	0.06	0.06	0.28	1.00	1092	1900
$\Delta H=50\div 60$ cm	0.40	0.09	0.22	0.58	1.00	2170	2461
$\Delta H=60\div 100$ cm	0.25	0.08	0.09	0.41	1.00	1976	2723
$\Delta H>100$ cm	0.53	0.07	0.39	0.66	1.00	1519	2450
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=5\div 10$ cm	0.42	0.05	0.32	0.52	1.00	817	1457
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=10\div 15$ cm	0.61	0.05	0.51	0.71	1.00	822	1477
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=15\div 20$ cm	0.52	0.06	0.41	0.64	1.00	1031	1862
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=20\div 30$ cm	0.61	0.07	0.48	0.73	1.00	1154	1844
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=30\div 40$ cm	0.69	0.06	0.57	0.81	1.00	1087	1990
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=40\div 50$ cm	0.66	0.06	0.55	0.77	1.00	1054	1744
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=50\div 60$ cm	0.35	0.11	0.14	0.56	1.00	2469	2795
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H=60\div 100$ cm	0.41	0.08	0.25	0.58	1.00	1921	2566
$\log_{10}(H) \times \Delta H>100$ cm	-0.04	0.05	-0.14	0.07	1.00	1017	1732
Marginal $R^2 = 0.70$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.97$							

(B) Model: $\log_{10}NSWr \sim \log_{10}\Delta H + H_{CLASS} + (Species)$

	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept ($H < 5$ m)	1.58	0.09	1.41	1.75	1.00	1073	1651
$\log_{10}(\Delta H)$	-0.51	0.03	-0.57	-0.46	1.00	2066	2902
$H = 5 \div 10$ m	1.84	0.03	1.77	1.90	1.00	1533	2340
$H = 10 \div 15$ m	2.02	0.03	1.95	2.08	1.00	1468	2203
$H = 15 \div 20$ m	2.12	0.03	2.05	2.18	1.00	1565	2137
$H = 20 \div 30$ m	2.23	0.04	2.15	2.31	1.00	1645	2254
$H > 30$ m	2.50	0.12	2.25	2.74	1.00	2818	2431
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 5 \div 10$ m	-0.57	0.02	-0.62	-0.53	1.00	1565	2376
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 10 \div 15$ m	-0.60	0.02	-0.65	-0.56	1.00	1441	2141
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 15 \div 20$ m	-0.66	0.02	-0.70	-0.62	1.00	1523	2104
$\log_{10}(H) \times H = 20 \div 30$ m	-0.70	0.02	-0.75	-0.66	1.00	1570	2055
$\log_{10}(H) \times H > 30$ m	-0.76	0.09	-0.93	-0.58	1.00	2889	2462
Marginal $R^2 = 0.76$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.96$							

(C) Model: $\log_{10}SWrw \sim \log_{10}\Delta H + Division + (Species)$

	Estimate	Est. Error	l-95% CI	u-95% CI	Rhat	Bulk_ESS	Tail_ESS
Intercept (<i>Conifers</i>)	-1.02	0.07	-1.15	-0.88	1.00	1389	1975
$\log_{10}(\Delta H)$	0.92	0.03	0.87	0.98	1.00	3372	2753
<i>Angiosperms</i>	-1.76	0.19	-2.16	-1.40	1.00	2136	2368
$\log_{10}(\Delta H) \times \text{Angiosperms}$	1.18	0.08	1.02	1.34	1.00	2556	2286
Marginal $R^2 = 0.88$							
Conditional $R^2 = 0.92$							

Figure S1. Schematic representation of the hydraulic model (above), and comparison between model configurations differing in stem elongation rate (ΔH) (below).

Figure S2. Model prediction of the decline in ring conductance (K_{RING}) and increase in cumulative conductance (K_{CUM}) with the ring number (RN) counted from the stem periphery inwards.

Figure S3. Relationship between $NSWr$ and tree height (H) assessed for different classes of annual stem height increment ($\Delta H =$ cm/year). Symbols represent conifers (triangles) and angiosperms (circles). Coloured fitting lines are according to Table S3A. Black lines represent the model prediction under the scenario of conduit widening scaling of (A) $b=0$ and (B) $b=0.3$.

Figure S4. Relationship between $NSWr$ and ΔH assessed for different H classes. Symbols represent conifers (triangles) and angiosperms (circles). Coloured fitting lines are according to Table S3B. Black lines represent the model prediction under the scenario of conduit widening scaling of (A) $b=0$ and (B) $b=0.3$.

